

Chemical Investigation of *Ougeinia Dalbergioides*, Benth*

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Two pentacyclic triterpene alcohols, identified as lupcol and betulin, have been isolated in good yields from the light petroleum and ether extracts, respectively, of the bark of *Ougeinia dalbergioides* (Fam. Leguminosae). From the ethanolic extract, a saponin has been obtained which on hydrolysis furnishes another triterpene, characterised as β -amyrin; the sugar moiety has been shown to contain glucose and arabinose, the former predominating.

Ougeinia dalbergioides Benth (Hindi: Sandan, Marathi: Tiwas) is a moderate-sized, deciduous tree, found in abundance in the Western ghats of Maharashtra. Various medicinal properties have been reported¹ for the different parts of this plant. The stem-bark and leaves are stated to be toxic to some caterpillar pests. The bark, when incised, furnishes a kino-like exudation which is useful in diarrhoea, dysentery, and leprosy. A decoction is administered among the hill tribes, when the urine becomes highly coloured. The bark is also used as a fish poison.

Very little work appears to have been done with the various parts of this plant. From the acetone extract of the heartwood, Balkrishna *et al.*² reported isolation of homoferreirin (5, 7-dihydroxy-2', 4'-dimethoxyisoflavanone) and a new isoflavanone which was named as Ougenin. From various degradation experiments, the authors have established the structure of ougenin as 5, 2', 4'-trihydroxy-6-methyl-7-methoxyisoflavanone, thus showing the first example of a *C*-methylisoflavanone in nature. Besides these, they have also isolated another compound from the same source, which on complete methylation produced 5, 7, 2', 4'-tetramethoxyisoflavanone.

The present investigation was undertaken with the bark of *O. dalbergioides*, made available to us through the kind courtesy of the Forest Utilization Officer, Poona. The dry, powdered bark was successively extracted at the room temperature with light petroleum, ether, and rectified spirit. The light petroleum extract, obtained to the extent of 0.5%, on chromatography over alumina and subsequent crystallisation from ether-methanol provided colorless, flowery crystals, m.p. 210-11° (compound A). It is readily soluble in ether and benzene, but sparingly soluble in methanol, ethanol, and light petroleum. While no specific colour was observed with FeCl₃, the compound A responded to all the characteristic colour reactions of a triterpene. The uniformity of the substance was confirmed by thin-layer chromatography. It had the molecular formula C₃₀H₅₀O, having $[\alpha]_D^{20} +26^\circ$ (CHCl₃) and contained one active hydrogen. It did not show any UV absorption, but the IR spectrum showed bands at 3600 cm⁻¹, 1026 cm⁻¹ (OH), 880 cm⁻¹ (exocyclic double bond).

*N. C. L. Communication No. 816.

1. Chopra, "Glossary of Indian Medicinal Plants", 1956, p. 183.
2. *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1961, **20B**, 134.
3. Mukherjee *et al.*, *Science & Culture*, 1963, **29**, 151.

The compound A formed a monoacetate, $C_{32}H_{52}O_2$, m.p. 214-15°, $[\alpha]_D^{20} + 46^\circ$ ($CHCl_3$), which showed strong IR absorption bands at 1737 cm^{-1} and 1235 cm^{-1} (acetate). It also formed a benzoate, $C_{37}H_{54}O_2$, m.p. 263-64°, $[\alpha]_D^{20} + 62^\circ$ ($CHCl_3$) with benzoyl chloride and pyridine. The nuclear magnetic resonance integration spectrum taken in a Varian A-60 spectrophotometer of the compound A-acetate confirmed the presence of 52 protons in the molecule.

All these physical and chemical properties indicate similarity with that of lupeol, a pentacyclic triterpene alcohol. Compound A was finally compared with an authentic sample of lupeol when a superimposable IR band was obtained and there was no depression in the mixed m.p. of the compounds.

From the ether extract of the bark, after removal of the solvent completely, a semi-solid, light coloured material was obtained (yield 0.6%), which on further purification was found from thin-layer chromatography to be a mixture of two triterpenes. These were separated by careful chromatography over alumina when one of the compounds was identified as lupeol and the other one, on further chromatography and several crystallisations, was obtained as stout, colorless needles, m.p. 252-53° (compound B). Its homogeneity was confirmed from thin-layer chromatography. It is readily soluble in chloroform and acetone and moderately soluble in hot ethanol and ether but insoluble in light petroleum, CS_2 , and water. The molecular formula was established as $C_{30}H_{50}O_2$, having $[\alpha]_D^{21} + 18.5^\circ$ ($CHCl_3$). Like lupeol, this substance also responded to all the characteristic colour reactions of a triterpene, but did not exhibit colour with $FeCl_3$. It showed presence of two active hydrogens in the molecule. The IR spectrum showed absorption bands at 3460 cm^{-1} , 1037 cm^{-1} (OH group), 1640 cm^{-1} ($-C=C-$), and 880 cm^{-1} (exocyclic double bond).

Compound B formed a diacetate, $C_{34}H_{54}O_4$, m.p. 218-19°, $[\alpha]_D^{20} + 24^\circ$ ($CHCl_3$), which showed strong IR absorption at 1735 cm^{-1} , 1235 cm^{-1} (acetate), 893 cm^{-1} (external double bond). It also formed a dibenzoate, $C_{44}H_{58}O_4$, m.p. 180-81°, $[\alpha]_D^{20} + 42^\circ$ ($CHCl_3$), with benzoyl chloride and pyridine. The total proton counts in the NMR integration spectrum of compound B-acetate correspond to 54, thus establishing the parent compound B having 50 protons.

Compound B was then compared with an authentic sample of betulin, when superimposable IR spectra were obtained and there was no depression in the mixed m.p. of the compounds. The well-known betulin—*allo*-betulin transformation was also carried out and compound B was definitely established as betulin.*

The ethanolic extract of the bark, after extraction with light petroleum and ether, was found to contain a good amount of saponin which could not be crystallised. The saponin was then hydrolysed with $EtOH-H_2SO_4$, when a brownish precipitate was obtained. This was Soxhleted with chloroform, which after chromatography yielded a colorless substance, crystallising from ether-methanol as colorless needles, m.p. 191-92° (compound C). This compound also was found to be a triterpene from the colour reactions

*While the work was completed, a note³ appeared in *Science & Culture* about the chemical examination of *O. dalbergioides* and it was mentioned that besides lupeol, the authors isolated another triterpene, m.p. 247-50° having $[\alpha]_D + 35.2^\circ$ ($CHCl_3$), which from the report appeared to be different from betulin. As such, we had to repeat our work, but we have always found compound B to be identical in all respects with betulin.

etc. Its analysis corresponded to $C_{30}H_{50}O$ having $[\alpha]_D^{20} + 83^\circ$ ($CHCl_3$). It showed the characteristic absorption bands for hydroxyl, but no bands for exocyclic double bond. It formed a monoacetate, $C_{34}H_{54}O_2$, m.p. $237-38^\circ$, $[\alpha]_D^{20} + 82^\circ$ ($CHCl_3$), and a monobenzoate, $C_{37}H_{54}O_2$, m.p. $228-29^\circ$, $[\alpha]_D^{20} + 80^\circ$ ($CHCl_3$). The NMR spectrum of the compound C-acetate also confirmed the presence of 50 protons in compound C.

From all the physical and chemical properties, the compound appears to be identical with β -amyrin. That it is not α -amyrin was ruled out from the study of IR spectra of authentic α - and β -amyryns. Compound C exhibited a superimposable IR spectrum with authentic β -amyrin and there was no depression in the mixed m.p. of the mixture of the two.

The filtrate from the acid-hydrolysis of the saponin was neutralised with $BaCO_3$, concentrated, and examined for the different sugar constituents by the usual paper chromatographic technique. Two sugars were found to be present which were identified as glucose and arabinose, the former predominating.

EXPERIMENTAL

The dry, powdered bark (3 kg.) was extracted with petroleum (b.p. $40-60^\circ$) at the room temperature until there was any appreciable amount in the extract. The solvent was distilled under reduced pressure and the resulting semisolid mass (15 g., 0.5%) was chromatographed with alumina and eluted with light petroleum and benzene. The benzene eluate yielded an almost colorless solid (3 g.) which was chromatographed once more and finally crystallised from ether-methanol, when colorless flowery clusters were obtained, m.p. $210-11^\circ$. This is named as compound A. (Found dried over P_2O_5 at 100° for 6 hr. under vacuum: C, 84.09; H, 11.9. Calc. for $C_{30}H_{50}O$: C, 84.40; H, 11.80%).

Acetylation of Compound A.—The substance (150 mg.) was warmed with acetic anhydride (7 ml) and pyridine (0.5 ml) on a water bath for 2 hr. and left overnight. Ice-water was then added to it when a solid separated which was filtered, washed well, and dried. It was crystallised from ether-light petroleum in fine colorless needles, m.p. $214-15^\circ$. (Found dried over P_2O_5 at 100° for 5 hr. under vacuum: C, 81.80, 82.06; H, 11.30, 11.50; COMe, 9.30; M.W., 445. Calc. for $C_{32}H_{52}O_2$: C, 81.99; H, 11.18; COMe, 9.10%; M.W., 468.7).

Benzoylation of Compound A.—The substance (90 mg.) was dissolved in freshly distilled pyridine (1 ml) and to the cooled solution was added benzoyl chloride (2 ml). Immediately there was a precipitate. The whole thing was heated on a water bath for 1 hr., cooled, and poured on ice-water. It was extracted with ether, the ethereal layer washed repeatedly with a solution of sodium carbonate and then with water, and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The residue after removal of the solvent was crystallised from ethanol in colorless flowery crystals, m.p. $263-64^\circ$. (Found dried over P_2O_5 at 100° for 6 hr. under vacuum: C, 83.40; H, 10.01. Calc. for $C_{37}H_{54}O_2$: C, 83.72; H, 10.25%).

After defatting the bark with light petroleum, it was extracted with ether at the room temperature until the ether extract did not have any appreciable residue. The total extract (17.5 g., 0.6%) after removal of the solvent was obtained as a light yellow solid which was purified by chromatography. But it was observed that the solid was a mixture of two components which were carefully separated by chromatography. From

light petroleum-benzene (95:5 and 90:10) fractions a compound was obtained which on crystallisation had m.p. 210-11° and was eventually found to be identical with compound A, i.e. lupeol. The second compound was obtained from the benzene eluate and was finally crystallised from light petroleum-ether, when it was obtained as colorless stout needles, m.p. 252-53° (compound B). (Found dried over P_2O_5 at 100° for 6 hr. under vacuum: C, 81.20; H, 11.30. Calc. for $C_{30}H_{50}O_2$: C, 81.39; H, 11.38%). Its IR spectrum in nujol was also studied.

Acetylation of compound B in the usual way yielded an acetyl derivative, crystallising from ether-light petroleum as colorless shining needles, m.p. 218-19°. (Found dry: C, 77.84; H, 10.77; COMe, 15.78. Calc. for $C_{34}H_{54}O_4$: C, 77.52; H, 10.33; COMe, 16.35%).

Benzoylation of compound B in the same way as in the case of compound A provided benzoylated derivative of compound B which was purified by chromatography over Al_2O_3 and finally crystallised from ethanol in colorless flowery crystals, m.p. 180-81°. (Found dried over P_2O_5 at 100° for 6 hr. under vacuum: C, 81.00; H, 8.90. Calc. for $C_{44}H_{76}O_4$: C, 81.19; H, 8.98%).

Action of Formic Acid on Compound B.—Compound B (400 mg.) was refluxed with formic acid (15 ml, 93%) for 1½ hr. at 140-45°. After working up the reaction mixture, a product was obtained which was crystallised from benzene as stout rhombic prisms, m.p. 309-10°. (Found dry: C, 78.80; H, 10.80. $C_3H_5O_3$ requires C, 79.10; H, 10.71%).

Alkaline Hydrolysis of the Formate.—The above formate was refluxed with EtOH-KOH solution to which benzene was added. After the reaction was over, benzene and ethanol were distilled and the precipitate formed was cooled, filtered, washed, and dried. It was crystallised from ethanol in colorless stout needles, m.p. 260-61°; $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 47^\circ$ ($CHCl_3$). (Found: C, 81.30; H, 11.20. Calc. for $C_{30}H_{50}O_2$: C, 81.39; H, 11.38%).

Acetylation of the above Isomerised Product.—On acetylation of the above compound in the usual way, only a monoacetyl derivative was obtained, crystallising from ether as colorless needles, m.p. 278-79°.

The bark, after extraction with light petroleum and ether, was further extracted with rectified spirit at the room temperature exhaustively. A brown resinous solid (12.5 g., 0.4%) was obtained after complete removal of the solvent. That it contained saponin, was evident from the behaviour with water, when a permanent froth was obtained. This saponin was purified by ethanol-ether (charcoaling) in the usual way but could not be crystallised though it was obtained as an almost colorless powder. The saponin was therefore hydrolysed with 2N- H_2SO_4 and the brown aglycone obtained was extracted with $CHCl_3$. It was purified by chromatography and crystallisation. It was crystallised from ether-methanol as colorless needles, m.p. 191-92°. This was named as compound C. [Found dried over P_2O_5 at 100° for 6 hr. under vacuum: C, 83.90; H, 11.70. $C_{30}H_{50}O$ requires C, 84.40; H, 11.80%).

Acetylation of Compound C.—It could be acetylated in the usual way; it was crystallised from ether-light petroleum as colorless shining needles, m.p. 237-38°. (Found: C, 81.70; H, 11.30. $C_{32}H_{52}O_2$ requires C, 81.80; H, 11.10%). The acetate bands were also observed in the IR spectrum of the compound.

Benzoylation of Compound C.—The benzoyl derivative was prepared as in the earlier case. It was crystallised from ether-light petroleum as colorless shining needles, m.p. 228-29°.

The sugar moiety from the hydrolysis of the saponin was characterised by neutralising the solution with BaCO₃; the filtrate was concentrated by charcoaling; the concentrate was used for identification of the sugars. Both the circular paper chromatography and the descending chromatogram were used. In the former case, the solvent system *n*-butanol-acetone: water (20:70:20) was used and aniline-diphenylamine-phosphoric acid (5:5:1) was used as the spraying reagent. In the latter case, the solvent system used was *n*-butanol-water-ethanol (5:1:4) and aniline hydrogen phthalate was made use of as the spraying agent. In both the cases, two sugars were found to be present which were compared with glucose and arabinose and were found to be identical. Glucose was found to be present predominantly..

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